

SOMONIYLAR DAVLATIDA HARBIYLARGA BERILGAN E'TIBOR VA HARBIY SAN'AT

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Somoniylar davlatidagi harbiy qo'shin tuzilishi, harbiylarga berilgan e'tibor, ularning yurishlardagi faoliyati haqida yanada kengroq yoritgan holatda fikrlar bildirib o'tilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: Somoniylar, qo'shin, gvardiya, viloyat, Ishtaxriy, Ibn Havqal, Hojib ul-hojib, sipahsolor, Movarounnahr, Xuroson, Hojib, Xaylboshi, Visoqboshi, g'ulom.

THE ATTENTION GIVEN TO THE MILITARY AND MILITARY ART IN THE SAMANID STATE

Abstract. In this article, the structure of the military forces in the Samanid state, the attention paid to the military, and their activities in campaigns are discussed in a more comprehensive manner.

Key words: Somanites, army, guard, province, Ishtakhri, Ibn Havqal, Hajib ul-Hajib, sipahsolor, Movarounnahr, Khurasan, Hajib, Khaylbashi, Visokbashi, ghulam.

ВНИМАНИЕ, УДЕЛЯЕМОЕ ВОЕННОМУ ДЕЛУ И ВОЕННОМУ ИСКУССТВУ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕ САМАНИДОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье более подробно рассматривается структура вооруженных сил в государстве Саманидов, внимание, уделяемое военным, их деятельность в походах.

Ключевые слова: соманиты, армия, гвардия, провинция, Иштахри, Ибн Хавкал, Хаджиб уль-Хаджиб, сипахсор, Моваруннахр, Хорасан, Хаджиб, Хайлбаши, Високбаши, гулам.

Somoniylar davlatida harbiylarga berilgan e'tibor va harbiy san'at

Ilk o'rta asrlar davrida natural xo'jalik va mulkdorlarning bosh-boshdoqligi katta muntazam qo'shin saqlash imkonini bermagan. Bu davrdagi harbiy hokimiyat bevosita yer-mulki bilan bog'liq edi. Movarounnahrning o'rta asrlardagi barcha mayda mulklarida ham uchratish mumkin edi. Faqatgina Somoniylar davrida mulkchilikning rivojlanishi, shaharlarning o'sishi, davlat boshqaruvining markazlashuvi bilangina Somoniylar saroyidagi ko'p sonli xos qism (gvardiya) asosida muntazam yollanma qo'shin tashkil qilish imkoni tug'ilgan.

Viloyat va tumanlardagi mahalliy hokimlarga tegishli lashkarlar ancha vaqtgacha mavjud bo'lgan. Somoniylar qo'shini doimiy muntazam xos qism va muvaqqat lashkarlarga bo'lingan.

Davlat va shoh saroyi hayotida turk g'ulomlaridan tuzilgan saroy gvardiyasi katta rol o'ynagan. Gvardiya tevarak atrofdagi Markaziy Osiyo viloyatlarining harbiy jihatdan yaxshi ta'lim olgan yoshlaridan tarkib topgan. Somoniylar davrida saroy g'ulomlarining tartib-qoidalari quyidagicha bo'lgan: g'ulomlarning mansablari xizmatlari katta- kichikligi, obro'-etiboriga qarab asta-sekin, darajama-daraja oshirib borilgan; g'ulomni sotib olgach, unga bir yil mobaynida piyoda askar bo'lib xizmat qilishni buyurishgan va u zandonichidan tayyorlangan qabo (ustki kiyim, chakmon) kiyib mulozimlar safida yurgan. Bu g'ulomlarga yashirin yoki oshkora suratda shu yil ichida otga minishga ruxsat etilmagan.

Agarda bilib qolinsa, ular jazolanganlar. Shunday suratda bir yil xizmatni o'tagach, visoqboshi hojib bilan gaplashgan; hojib g'ulomga yurgan va oddiy tasma berish haqida ko'rsatma bergan. Qachonki u ot va qamchi bilan yana bir yil xizmat qilgach, kelgusi yili unga beliga o'rash uchun qorajo'r (qiyiqcha) berilgan. Beshinchi yilga kelib unga yaxshi egar, yulduzlar shakli bilan naqshlangan yugan, doroi qabo va gurzi berilgan, gurzini u halqaga ilib qo'ygan. Oltinchi yili u anvoi kiyim, yettinchi yili bir qubbali, 16 qoziqli chodir ilgan, uning ixtiyoriga uchta g'ulom berilgan va u visoqboshi deyilgan. U qora kigizga nuqra (kumush) bezaklar tikilgan qalpoq va ganja qabosi kiygan yil sayin uning obro'-e'tibori, bezagi, qo'shini, unvonlari oshib xaylboshi, so'ng hojib bo'lgan; garchi uning fazilatlar odamoxun va hojasiga muhabbatli bo'lsada, toki 37 yoshga yetgunga qadar unga amirlik mansabi hamda yer-mulki ajratib berilmagan.

Somoniylarning quli va tarbiyalanuvchisi bo'lgan Alptegin 35 yoshda Xurosondagi sipohsolorlikni olgan. U 2700 jangchi g'ulomga qo'mondonlik qilib, Movarounnahr va Xurosonda ulkan boylikka egalik qilgan.

Xos qism bilan bir qatorda, lozim bo'lganda yana Movarounnahr va Xurosonning ayrim mahalliy viloyat hokimlaridan ko'p sonli lashkarlar to'plangan. Ishtaxriyning xabar berishiga qaraganda, mamlakat ayrim okruglarga (kulob) ajratilgan bo'lib ular lashkar uchun ma'lum miqdorda jangchilar ajratishgan. Lashkarlarning harbiy qobiliyati yuqori edi. Lashkar tashqi harbiy xavf tug'ilganda, ichki nizolar isyonlar paytida va ko'chmanchilarga qarshi yurish tashkil etilayotganda to'plangan lashkarlar o'z hisobidan, mahalliy hokimlar hisoblaridan ta'minlangan va davlat qaramog'ida bo'lgan. Qurol-aslaha va oziq-ovqat bilan ta'minlash bevosita ma'lum vazifaga bog'liq edi. Qo'shin tarkibida turkiy ko'chmanchi qabilalardan tuzulgan yollanma qismlar ham bo'lgan. Chegarani mahalliy hokimlar lashkarlari va g'oziyalar harbiy bo'linmalari himoya qilgan. Davlat hokimiyatining asosiy tayanchini Somoniylarning ko'p sonli turkiy gvardiyasi tashkil qilgan.

Zaruriyat tug'ulganda somoniy amirlari viloyat va tumanlardan ko'ngilli lashkarlardan katta qo'shin to'plashgan. Gvardiyaning mahalliy aholi bilan umumiy manfaati o'xshash emasdi, ular maoshni markaziy xazinadan olardi, shuning uchun somoniylarning ancha ishonchli tayanchi edi. Lashkarlar harbiy xizmatni o'tash chog'ida, - deb yozadi Ibn Havqal, oziq-ovqat bilan yaxshi ta'minlanadi, hukumat ularga g'amxo'rlik qilib turadi. Maqdisiy somoniylar davlatining yarim mustaqil viloyati bo'lgan Chag'oniyon viloyatini tasvirlab, bu viloyat "o'n mingga yaqin lashkarni o'z kiyim-kechagi, ozig'i va o'z otlari bilan yetkazib berar edi", deb yozadi. Lashkarlarning ta'minlanishi, aftidan, aniq vaziyatga bog'liq bo'lsa kerak: ba'zi viloyatlarda lashkarlar o'zlarini ko'proq, ba'zida kamroq ta'minlab turgan bo'lishlari mumkin. Harbiy yurishlar vaqtida esa ularni asosan hukumat ta'minlab turganlar.

Hojib ul-hojib-somoniyalarda bosh qo'mondonlik qilgan. Bu lavozimlar turkiylardan tayinlangan.

Siphsolor-amirlikda qo'shin qo'mondon.

Ariz-somoniyalarda qo'shin ta'minoti bilan shug'ullanuvchi shaxs

Pushtig'bon- tan soqchilik qilgan. Faqat amirga bo'ysungan va amirni himoyalagan.

Hojib-harbiy boshliq yoki zobit.

Xaylboshi-o'nlik tizim zobiti.

Visoqboshi-to'rt nafarli askariy guruh boshlig'i, chodir boshlig'i.

Bahodir Eshovning O'zbek davlatchiligi va boshqaruvi tarixi kitobida shunday yozilgan.

Nizomulmulkning Siyosatnoma asarida yozilishicha, uch nafar g'ulom berilgan. Bundan tashqari o'n olti qoziqli chodir berilgan. U qora kigizga nuqra (kumush) bezaklar tikilgan qalpoq va ganja qabosi kiygan.

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